

Beyond the triple product: fusion rate enhancement and nuclear reaction engineering

White Paper

Dr. Florian Metzler
MIT

June 2026

This white paper situates fusion reaction rate enhancement within a broader class of efforts to modify nuclear reaction dynamics rather than only improve temperature, density, and confinement time as the so-called triple product. It reviews the standard Gamow-factor / S-factor framing of nuclear fusion, identifies key modeling forks that any proposed fusion enhancement mechanism must address, compares adjacent literatures on fusion rate enhancement, and recommends a fail-fast de-risking path focused on benchmarking, order-of-magnitude estimates, controls, and go/no-go criteria. The broader motivation is nuclear reaction engineering: the deliberate control of nuclear reaction rates and nuclear reaction products using fields, materials, collective effects, nuclear-state preparation, and resonance engineering.

Contents

Executive summary	2
1 Context: standard fusion rate modeling	3
2 Key modeling question: does going beyond Gamow reveal new levers?	3
3 Adjacent literatures and expected enhancement scales	4
3.1 Spin-polarized fusion	5
3.2 Nuclear structure resonances	5
3.3 Static electron screening	5
3.4 Mechanical / environmental modulation of proximity and electron screening	6
3.5 Field-biased / strong-field fusion modification	6
3.6 Accelerating nuclear dynamics via collective quantum effects I: superradiance	7
3.7 Accelerating nuclear dynamics via collective quantum effects II: supertransfer	7
4 Discussion	7
5 Outlook	8
References	10

Executive summary

Fusion research has long been organized around the conventional “triple product” framing: temperature, density, and confinement time. This white paper takes a broader view. It asks whether part of the next frontier in fusion could involve modifying the nuclear reaction rates themselves, rather than only improving the macroscopic conditions under which reactions occur. This question sits within a larger emerging field that can be called nuclear reaction engineering: the deliberate control of nuclear reaction rates and nuclear reaction products using fields, materials, collective effects, nuclear-state preparation, and resonance engineering.

The standard method for estimating fusion rates separates Coulomb barrier tunneling, usually expressed through the Gamow factor and obtained via the WKB approximation, from the nuclear physics contribution, captured by the S-factor. This framework is simple and empirically successful in many plasma fusion contexts, but it is also reductionist: it typically treats the barrier as effectively radial and spherically symmetric, while much of modern nuclear physics emphasizes the internal structure of nuclei such as deuterons, including spin, tensor-force effects, S–D mixing, and the coupled-channel dynamics that appear when two nuclei approach and react.

Several adjacent literatures suggest possible control knobs: spin-polarized fusion, nuclear structure resonances, electron screening, environmental fluctuations, strong-field and dynamically assisted tunneling, nuclear superradiance, and collective excitation transfer. None of these literatures by itself establishes a mature technology. Collectively, however, they show that nuclear processes need not always be treated as immutable rates in isolation from their surrounding electronic, material, electromagnetic, and quantum environment.

A central high-priority challenge is the need for concrete nuclear fusion rate predictions and corresponding order-of-magnitude estimates of achievable enhancement over standard predictions. Canonical approaches for spontaneous D–D fusion under ambient conditions give rates on the order of 10^{-64} s^{-1} per deuteron pair in a molecular-scale configuration, while readily observable rates require roughly 10^{-20} s^{-1} or higher (Koonin and Nauenberg 1989; Metzler et al. 2024). This implies for instance that a room-temperature D–D fusion concept must plausibly bridge more than 40 orders of magnitude.

Existing adjacent literatures provide useful scale comparisons: spin-polarized fusion yields order-unity gains; strong-field approaches can predict multiple orders of magnitude for asymmetric reactions such as D–T under extreme assumptions, but not for D–D in uniform fields; fluctuation and screening approaches can formally produce large enhancements, but depend strongly on whether the required transient material configurations are physically plausible; nuclear resonance ideas may contribute several orders of magnitude; collective quantum effects such as superradiance are experimentally established for nuclear transitions, while related transfer-based fusion enhancement remains at an early stage of exploration.

The opportunity is real, but progress will depend on whether central modeling assumptions can be defended and benchmarked against the best existing nuclear theory, and whether intuitions can be made quantitative and converted into credible estimates of achievable enhancement. This motivates a fail-fast de-risking path: define the cleanest observable, benchmark against established theory, estimate the maximum plausible effect size, identify artifacts and controls, and specify what result would invalidate the hypothesis. Such a programmatic logic is essential if fusion reaction rate enhancement is to mature from a set of intriguing mechanisms into a rigorous component of nuclear science and engineering.

1 Context: standard fusion rate modeling

The standard method to estimate fusion reaction rates—such as for deuteron–deuteron fusion—emerged from Gamow’s 1928 barrier penetration work and early stellar fusion calculations by Atkinson and Houtermans in 1929, which matured into the modern Gamow-factor / S-factor formalism by the 1950s (Gamow 1928; Atkinson and Houtermans 1929; Salpeter 1952). This approach separates the fusion process into two major constituent parts: Coulomb barrier penetration, which is characterized by the so-called Gamow factor, and a separate factor accounting for the nuclear physics of the specific reaction, known as the S-factor. In this context, the WKB approximation provides a standard semiclassical estimate of the tunneling probability through an effective one-dimensional potential barrier.

This approach is conceptually and computationally simple and gives surprisingly accurate numbers when comparing with observed fusion rates in plasmas at medium to high energy ($\gg 1$ keV). The Gamow factor is dominated by the Coulomb potential, which is typically taken as spherically symmetric. S-factor values for different nuclear reaction pairs, such as D–T, D–D, and p– ^{11}B , have been catalogued and are largely derived from experimental data (Bosch and Hale 1992; Angulo et al. 1999; Xu et al. 2013).

The Gamow-factor / S-factor approach remains the dominant practical framework today, across research centers and fusion companies, to predict fusion rates and guide design decisions aimed at maximizing fusion yield. It is widely recognized as a reductionist picture, but in many practical contexts it is viewed as “good enough.”

In parallel, nuclear physics developed increasingly microscopic models of nuclear reactions, including realistic nucleon–nucleon interactions, cluster models, and microscopic reaction theory. These represent the basis for attempts to develop first-principles, or *ab initio*, models of nuclear fusion, seeking to do greater justice to the complexities of nuclei, nucleons, and the strong nuclear force (Epelbaum, Hammer, and Meißner 2009; Quaglioni et al. 2012).

This is the backdrop for a broader question: can fusion research move beyond satisfying plasma conditions alone and begin to ask whether nuclear reaction rates themselves can sometimes be modified, controlled, or enhanced?

2 Key modeling question: does going beyond Gamow reveal new levers?

The standard Gamow-factor / S-factor framework is the established starting point for fusion rate estimates. It is empirically successful in many beam-target and plasma fusion settings, and it will likely continue to serve as the workhorse model in such contexts. The question is, however, whether more detailed modeling approaches can reveal control variables that are hidden, averaged over, or not naturally represented in the simplified one-dimensional tunneling picture.

Stated more sharply: does the Gamow/S-factor approach already capture essentially all nuclear physics relevant for low-energy fusion and related reactions, leaving only macroscopic plasma parameters to optimize? Or can more microscopic and many-body descriptions identify new levers—spin preparation, channel selection, resonance structure, material environments, coherent collective states, oscillator exchange, or engineered loss channels—that could modify reaction rates, branching ratios, or final-state pathways?

Two modeling directions are especially important to compare.

First, modern *ab initio* and microscopic reaction theory treats low-energy fusion as a coupled few-body nuclear problem rather than as tunneling through a simple radial barrier. In D–D fusion, for example, the relevant problem is a four-nucleon scattering and rearrangement problem involving channels such as $d + d$, $p + t$, $n + ^3\text{He}$, and radiative or nonradiative routes toward ^4He . This literature already incorporates

spin, tensor forces, partial waves, channel coupling, and nuclear structure in a much more complete way than a simple Gamow estimate. It is therefore a natural benchmark for any claim that detailed nuclear modeling reveals exploitable new structure (Viviani et al. 2023; Deltuva and Fonseca 2010; Arai et al. 2011; Solov'yev et al. 2024).

Second, a Terhune-and-Baldwin-inspired Hamiltonian approach treats nuclei in solids not as isolated two-body reactors, but as parts of a larger quantized system containing internal nuclear states, lattice vibrations, electromagnetic fields, and material degrees of freedom (Terhune and Baldwin 1965). This line of thought has been developed further in models of solid-state fusion in which a fusion transition, such as a D–D to ^4He transition, is coupled to receiver nuclear states and lattice modes through a generalized nuclear Dicke model (Hagelstein et al. 2025). In plain language, this approach asks whether the material can do more than hold nuclei close together: can it provide resonant receivers, collective enhancement, oscillator energy exchange, or loss channels that change how nuclear energy is routed?

These two modeling directions are complementary. *Ab initio* reaction theory asks whether there are overlooked nuclear-structure levers in the reaction itself. The many-body Hamiltonian approach asks whether embedding the nuclear transition in a structured material and field environment creates additional pathways not present in an isolated two-body treatment. Both must still reduce to quantitative predictions: rates, branching ratios, product distributions, or a clear bound on why no meaningful enhancement is expected.

These considerations suggest a generic de-risking agenda:

- **Benchmark the baseline.** What does the standard Gamow/S-factor treatment predict for the relevant reaction, and over what energy range is it experimentally constrained?
- **Ask what is already included.** Are the proposed effects already absorbed into the empirical S-factor, established screening corrections, or modern reaction-theory calculations?
- **Identify the new variable.** What physical control knob is being introduced—spin polarization, electronic screening, a nuclear resonance, coherent excitation, lattice motion, a driven field, a receiver-state manifold, or an engineered loss channel?
- **Close the rate loop.** How many orders of magnitude of enhancement can the mechanism plausibly produce under favorable assumptions, and how does that compare with the $\sim 10^{-64} \text{ s}^{-1}$ molecular D–D benchmark from Koonin and Nauenberg (1989) and the observable rate threshold discussed by Metzler et al. (2024)?
- **Define the observable.** Does the mechanism predict a clean change in total rate, branching ratio, product distribution, delayed nuclear signal, heat/particle correlation, or excitation-transfer signature?
- **Specify go/no-go criteria.** What calculation or experiment would show that the proposed lever is too small, already accounted for, or not experimentally accessible?

The purpose of this modeling discussion is to define a disciplined test: either more complete nuclear and material Hamiltonians reveal genuine control variables, or they show that the simplified Gamow/S-factor approach is already sufficient for the relevant conditions. Both outcomes would be valuable. The first would open a path toward nuclear reaction engineering; the second would prevent wasted effort and clarify where not to look.

3 Adjacent literatures and expected enhancement scales

The approach of two nuclei is famously hindered by the Coulomb barrier, which in typical fusion configurations is not “overcome” in the classical sense but tunneled through. The tunneling probability is a function of the potential and the relative energy of the fusion reactants, which determines the “attack height” of the barrier. At temperatures on the order of 10 keV, the potential is narrow and the tunneling probability is substantial; it decreases rapidly at lower temperatures. Room temperature corresponds

to sub-eV energies for deuterons, where the tunneling probability is extremely small but nevertheless nonzero. Koonin and Nauenberg (1989) provide a canonical estimate for D–D fusion at room temperature, reporting about $3 \times 10^{-64} \text{ s}^{-1}$ per deuteron pair at 74 pm proximity, the D_2 molecular distance. Observable levels of fusion require rates closer to 10^{-20} s^{-1} or higher, defining the challenge as achieving more than 40 orders of magnitude of enhancement (Metzler et al. 2024).

3.1 Spin-polarized fusion

One conceptually adjacent precedent is spin-polarized fusion. Spin-polarized fusion has focused on the widely pursued D–T reaction, which for unpolarized spin combinations goes through both the faster $S = 3/2$ channel and the slower $S = 1/2$ channel. Preparing the deuterium and tritium nuclei so that their spins are aligned in parallel favors the entrance channel total spin $3/2$ configuration. This approach has been estimated to yield a cross section and fusion rate enhancement of about $1.5\times$ under idealized conditions (Paetz gen. Schieck 2010; Hupin, Quaglioni, and Navrátil 2019).

Selection of key references:

- Hupin, Quaglioni, and Navrátil, “Ab Initio Predictions for Polarized Deuterium-Tritium Thermonuclear Fusion,” *Nature Communications* 10, 351 (2019).
- Paetz gen. Schieck, “The Status of ‘Polarized Fusion’,” *European Physical Journal A* 44, 321–354 (2010).

3.2 Nuclear structure resonances

A conceptually adjacent literature argues that enhanced D–D fusion rates could arise from previously underappreciated structure in the compound ^4He system near the $d + d$ threshold. In this view, the relevant physics is a resonant four-nucleon state that modifies the low-energy reaction amplitude, branching ratios, and possible decay channels. Czerski (2022) attributes about seven orders of magnitude of fusion rate enhancement to such a hypothesized resonance at low energy.

Selection of key references:

- Czerski, “Deuteron-Deuteron Nuclear Reactions at Extremely Low Energies,” *Physical Review C* 106, L011601 (2022).
- Czerski et al., “Observation of Thermal Deuteron-Deuteron Fusion in Ion Tracks,” arXiv:2409.02112 (2024).

3.3 Static electron screening

A well-established adjacent literature studies how electrons reduce the Coulomb repulsion between nuclei. In the simplest treatment, electron screening lowers the Coulomb barrier by a screening energy U_e , which yields equivalent results for barrier penetration as if this screening energy were added to the relative kinetic energy of the reactants. In metals, theoretical screening values are estimated up to about 150 eV, with Pd near the upper end. For molecule-like proximity of D_2 , such static metal screening can enhance D–D fusion rates by roughly 20 orders of magnitude relative to unscreened estimates. Locally enhanced static screening at defect sites or electronic environments with high effective electron mass has been conjectured to add up to another ~ 15 orders of magnitude, but this is less established and requires further modeling and experimental validation (Raiola et al. 2006; Huke et al. 2008; Metzler et al. 2024).

Selection of key references:

- Raiola et al., “Electron Screening: A Review,” *AIP Conference Proceedings* 831, 296–303 (2006).

- Shoppa, Koonin, Langanke, and Seki, “One- and Two-Electron Atomic Screening in Fusion Reactions,” *Physical Review C* 48, 837–840 (1993).
- Huke et al., “Enhancement of Deuteron-Fusion Reactions in Metals and Experimental Implications,” *Physical Review C* 78, 015803 (2008).
- Czerski et al., “Screening and Resonance Enhancements of the ${}^2\text{H}(d, p){}^3\text{H}$ Reaction Yield in Metallic Environments,” *Europhysics Letters* 113, 22001 (2016).

3.4 Mechanical / environmental modulation of proximity and electron screening

A separate adjacent literature focuses on condensed matter fluctuations or driven material dynamics that transiently improve tunneling conditions. Koonin (1989) framed this as averaging the instantaneous fusion rate over fluctuations in the effective potential, where temporary barrier minima can dominate. Fork et al. (2020) propose an engineered version in which plasmon oscillations create transient regions of high electron density with enhanced screening beyond static screening limits. For realistic fluctuations of deuterons in a lattice on the order of 5 pm, Koonin predicts an expected D–D fusion rate enhancement of roughly eight orders of magnitude. Fork et al. predict transient screening potential increases of about 40%, which would correspond to roughly 15 orders of magnitude of fusion rate enhancement (Metzler et al. 2024).

Selection of key references:

- Koonin, “Enhancement of Cold Fusion Rates by Fluctuations,” NSF-ITP-89-55; submitted to *Physical Review Letters* (1989).
- Fork, Munday, Narayan, and Murray, “Enhanced Electron Screening through Plasmon Oscillations,” US Patent 10,566,094 B2 (2020).

3.5 Field-biased / strong-field fusion modification

Another adjacent literature studies whether intense time-dependent electromagnetic fields can modify fusion probabilities by changing relative nuclear motion. One caveat is that this approach primarily applies to asymmetric fusion reactions such as D–T, since in symmetric reactions such as D–D both reactants are affected equally by an applied uniform field. Qi, Zhou, and Wang (2026) predict up to about nine orders of magnitude enhancement for D–T fusion under intense low-frequency laser irradiation, broadly consistent with Queisser and Schützhold (2019)’s earlier estimate of up to about ten orders under favorable strong-field assumptions. Qi et al. also find no enhancement for D–D fusion due to the symmetry of the reactants. Ryndyk et al. (2024)’s explicit Floquet treatment finds much more modest enhancement, about 10% for the D–T case.

Selection of key references:

- Queisser and Schützhold, “Dynamically Assisted Nuclear Fusion,” *Physical Review C* 100, 041601 (2019).
- Kohlfürst, Queisser, and Schützhold, “Dynamically Assisted Tunneling in the Impulse Regime,” *Physical Review Research* 3, 033153 (2021).
- Ryndyk, Kohlfürst, Queisser, and Schützhold, “Dynamically Assisted Tunneling in the Floquet Picture,” *Physical Review Research* 6, 023056 (2024).
- Lindsey, Bekx, and Schlesinger, “Dynamically Assisted Nuclear Fusion in the Strong-Field Regime,” *Physical Review C* 109, 044605 (2024).
- Qi, Zhou, and Wang, “Theory of Laser-Assisted Nuclear Fusion,” *Nuclear Science and Techniques* 37, 53 (2026).

3.6 Accelerating nuclear dynamics via collective quantum effects I: superradiance

A relevant nuclear quantum optics literature shows that nuclear transition dynamics can be accelerated when many resonant nuclei couple coherently to a shared radiation mode. Terhune and Baldwin (1965) argued in 1965 that nuclei in a regular lattice should be treated as an integrated quantized system coupled through electromagnetic and phonon fields, rather than as independent nuclei. Röhlberger et al. (2010) later demonstrated nuclear superradiance in ^{57}Fe , with measured decay-speedup of about two orders of magnitude. This literature does not directly imply fusion rate enhancement, but it establishes that collective phase-coherent nuclear ensembles can exhibit transition dynamics very different from independent nuclei.

Selection of key references:

- Terhune and Baldwin, “Nuclear Superradiance in Solids,” *Physical Review Letters* 14, 589–591 (1965).
- Röhlberger et al., “Collective Lamb Shift in Single-Photon Superradiance,” *Science* 328, 1248–1251 (2010).
- Heeg et al., “Coherent X-Ray–Optical Control of Nuclear Excitons,” *Nature* 590, 401–404 (2021).

3.7 Accelerating nuclear dynamics via collective quantum effects II: supertransfer

An adjacent literature asks whether collective enhancement can not only cause accelerated emission but also accelerated excitation transfer between nuclear systems, known as supertransfer. Lilley et al. (2026) show how nuclei coupled via long-wavelength driven fields can exhibit collective enhancement factors over large volumes, predicting observable nonradiative nuclear excitation transfer across ^{57}Fe nuclei. Hagelstein et al. (2025) apply this approach to D–D fusion in solids, proposing that a deuteron pair transition to ^4He can transfer its energy to resonant or near-resonant states of nearby nuclei, mediated by lattice modes. They predict that enhancements of 40+ orders of magnitude are possible under favorable conditions.

Selection of key references:

- Lilley et al., “Stimulated Nuclear Excitation Transfer,” forthcoming manuscript (2026).
- Hagelstein et al., “Models for Nuclear Fusion in the Solid State,” arXiv:2501.08338 (2025).
- Lloyd and Mohseni, “Symmetry-Enhanced Supertransfer of Delocalized Quantum States,” *New Journal of Physics* 12, 075020 (2010).

4 Discussion

The broader aspiration to identify non-brute-force routes to fusion is commendable. Critique of overly reductionist fusion-rate models is legitimate, and it is reasonable to ask whether richer treatments of nuclear structure, nuclear state preparation, electronic screening, lattice dynamics, and environmental control could reveal new opportunities. It is not implausible that more microscopic modeling of nuclear reactions could eventually lead to insights of technological relevance.

At the same time, this is a technically difficult area in which roadmapping is not straightforward. More work is needed to define what concrete and credible projects would look like within limited time and resources, and where such projects sit in relation to existing work in nuclear theory.

For detailed modeling approaches, the central technical issue is whether the additional structure introduced by the model produces a real control variable or merely restates physics already contained in established reaction theory or empirical S-factors. If a new lever is identified, the next step should be to close the loop between the model and an actual rate, branching ratio, or product distribution estimate. This requires quantifying the maximum enhancement under favorable assumptions, identifying the conditions under

which the lever is experimentally accessible, and comparing the resulting rate per deuteron pair to the $\sim 10^{-64} \text{ s}^{-1}$ molecular D–D benchmark from Koonin and Nauenberg (1989).

This broader space contains many interesting ideas, but many proposed enhancement mechanisms become insufficient once evaluated quantitatively against the many orders of magnitude by which low-energy fusion is hindered. For this reason, a fail-fast approach is essential: move quickly toward upper-bound, order-of-magnitude estimates of the maximum achievable enhancement under favorable assumptions. If such estimates fall far short of the required 40+ orders of magnitude, the concept should be reconsidered or combined with other relevant concepts.

Scientific credibility will depend on sustained engagement with the relevant expert communities, but this is not only about external perception. It is also directly in the interest of teams working in this area. Early dialog with nuclear theorists, fusion modelers, condensed matter physicists, quantum optics experts, detector specialists, and experimentalists can surface relevant prior work, identify hidden assumptions, reveal possible mistakes, and suggest more promising formulations. This kind of feedback can prevent months or years of avoidable work.

Publishing manuscripts or articles can play a useful role because it forces the argument into a structured form and enables technical dialog. Concerns about intellectual property can often be addressed through provisional patent filings where appropriate, rather than through prolonged secrecy. A manuscript draft often clarifies what is potentially patentable; a provisional application can then secure an early priority date at low cost while still allowing teams to seek expert feedback, de-risk the concept, and avoid committing significant resources before basic technical objections have been addressed.

Overall, fusion reaction rate enhancement is a high-risk but intellectually legitimate frontier. The most important near-term task is to develop a disciplined comparison of mechanisms, effect sizes, assumptions, observables, and go/no-go criteria. That kind of work is a necessary step toward nuclear reaction engineering: the deliberate control of nuclear rates, pathways, and products by fields, materials, collective effects, state preparation, and resonance engineering.

5 Outlook

A broad view of this emerging space is warranted. Much of the relevant knowledge base, experimental experience, and theoretical machinery cuts across the categories discussed above: deuteron-structure modeling, *ab initio* reaction theory, strong-field effects, electron screening, lattice dynamics, resonance physics, and collective quantum effects. As in many areas of science and technology, there may be convergence once it becomes clearer which approaches hold up quantitatively and which provide the most leverage.

What is lacking at present is a coherent community of research groups focused specifically on fusion rate enhancement and the broader control of nuclear reaction dynamics. There is a real opportunity to convene such groups, facilitate dialog, compare assumptions, identify shared technical bottlenecks, and build a common language across currently separate literatures. Such a process could be a precondition for proper field formation and, eventually, technology development.

Research funders and innovation agencies could play a constructive role by organizing workshops or challenge programs on fusion rate enhancement beyond the triple product. Such efforts could bring together nuclear theorists, fusion scientists, condensed matter physicists, quantum optics experts, metrologists, detector specialists, isotope-production groups, and relevant experimental groups working on low-energy nuclear reaction measurements. A useful outcome would be a short technical roadmap identifying the most plausible mechanisms, the most important open questions, and the experiments or calculations that could quickly rule mechanisms in or out.

More broadly, there is real potential for a next generation of fusion research focused not only on achieving

the right plasma conditions, but also on understanding whether fusion reaction dynamics themselves can be modified, controlled, or enhanced. This is still a high-risk area, but it is sufficiently grounded in adjacent established literatures to merit structured exploration. An early convening and de-risking effort could help determine a credible path forward.

References

- Angulo, C., M. Arnould, M. Rayet, P. Descouvemont, D. Baye, C. Leclercq-Willain, A. Coc, S. Barhoumi, P. Aguer, C. Rolfs, et al. 1999. "NACRE: A Compilation of Charged-Particle Induced Thermonuclear Reaction Rates." *Nuclear Physics A* 656 (1): 3–183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9474\(99\)00030-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0375-9474(99)00030-5).
- Arai, Koji, Shigeyoshi Aoyama, Yasuyuki Suzuki, Pierre Descouvemont, and Daniel Baye. 2011. "Tensor Force Manifestations in Ab Initio Study of the ${}^2\text{H}(d, \gamma){}^4\text{He}$, ${}^2\text{H}(d, p){}^3\text{H}$, and ${}^2\text{H}(d, n){}^3\text{He}$ Reactions." *Physical Review Letters* 107 (13): 132502. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.107.132502>.
- Atkinson, Robert d'Escourt, and Fritz G. Houtermans. 1929. "Zur Frage der Aufbaumöglichkeit der Elemente in Sternen." *Zeitschrift für Physik* 54:656–665. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01341590>.
- Bosch, H.-S., and G. M. Hale. 1992. "Improved Formulas for Fusion Cross-Sections and Thermal Reactivities." *Nuclear Fusion* 32 (4): 611–631. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0029-5515/32/4/I07>.
- Chumakov, A. I., et al. 2018. "Superradiance of an Ensemble of Nuclei Excited by a Free Electron Laser." *Nature Physics* 14:261–264. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-017-0001-z>.
- Czerski, Konrad. 2022. "Deuteron-Deuteron Nuclear Reactions at Extremely Low Energies." *Physical Review C* 106 (1): L011601. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.106.L011601>.
- Czerski, Konrad, Rakesh Dubey, Agata Kowalska, G. Haridas Das, M. Kaczmarski, N. Targosz-Slecza, and Mathieu Valat. 2024. *Observation of Thermal Deuteron-Deuteron Fusion in Ion Tracks*. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2409.02112>. arXiv: 2409.02112.
- Czerski, Konrad, Dirk Weissbach, A. I. Kiliç, G. Ruprecht, A. Huke, M. Kaczmarski, N. Targosz-Slecza, and K. Maass. 2016. "Screening and Resonance Enhancements of the ${}^2\text{H}(d, p){}^3\text{H}$ Reaction Yield in Metallic Environments." *Europhysics Letters* 113:22001. <https://doi.org/10.1209/0295-5075/113/22001>.
- Deltuva, A., and A. C. Fonseca. 2010. "Polarization Observables and Spin-Aligned Fusion Rates in ${}^2\text{H}(d, p){}^3\text{H}$ and ${}^2\text{H}(d, n){}^3\text{He}$ Reactions." *Physical Review C* 81 (5): 054002. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.81.054002>.
- Epelbaum, Evgeny, Hans-Werner Hammer, and Ulf-G. Meißner. 2009. "Modern Theory of Nuclear Forces." *Reviews of Modern Physics* 81 (4): 1773–1825. <https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.81.1773>.
- Fork, David K., Jeremy N. Munday, Tarun Narayan, and James B. Murray (Google LLC). 2020. Enhanced electron screening through plasmon oscillations US10566094B2, filed 2020.
- Gamow, George. 1928. "Zur Quantentheorie des Atomkernes." *Zeitschrift für Physik* 51:204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01343196>.
- Hagelstein, Peter L., Florian Metzler, Matt K. Lilley, Jonah F. Messinger, and Nicola Galvanetto. 2025. *Models for Nuclear Fusion in the Solid State*. Preprint. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2501.08338>. arXiv: 2501.08338.
- Heeg, Kilian P., et al. 2021. "Coherent X-Ray-Optical Control of Nuclear Excitons." *Nature* 590:401–404. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03276-x>.
- Huke, A., K. Czerski, P. Heide, G. Ruprecht, N. Targosz, and W. Zebrowski. 2008. "Enhancement of Deuteron-Fusion Reactions in Metals and Experimental Implications." *Physical Review C* 78 (1): 015803. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.78.015803>.
- Hupin, Guillaume, Sofia Quaglioni, and Petr Navrátil. 2019. "Ab Initio Predictions for Polarized Deuterium-Tritium Thermonuclear Fusion." *Nature Communications* 10:351. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-08052-6>.

- Keeble, Joseph W. T., and Arnau Rios. 2020. "Machine Learning the Deuteron." *Physics Letters B* 809:135743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2020.135743>.
- Kohlfürst, Christian, Friedemann Queisser, and Ralf Schützhold. 2021. "Dynamically Assisted Tunneling in the Impulse Regime." *Physical Review Research* 3 (3): 033153. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.3.033153>.
- Koonin, Steven E. 1989. *Enhancement of Cold Fusion Rates by Fluctuations*. NSF-ITP-89-55; submitted to Physical Review Letters.
- Koonin, Steven E., and Michael Nauenberg. 1989. "Calculated Fusion Rates in Isotopic Hydrogen Molecules." *Nature* 339:690. <https://doi.org/10.1038/339690a0>.
- Lilley, Matt K., Peter L. Hagelstein, Jonah F. Messinger, Matthew Decapua, Nicola Galvanetto, and Florian Metzler. 2026. "Stimulated Nuclear Excitation Transfer." Forthcoming manuscript.
- Lindsey, M. L., J. J. Bekx, and K.-G. Schlesinger. 2024. "Dynamically Assisted Nuclear Fusion in the Strong-Field Regime." *Physical Review C* 109 (4): 044605. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.109.044605>.
- Lloyd, Seth, and Masoud Mohseni. 2010. "Symmetry-Enhanced Supertransfer of Delocalized Quantum States." *New Journal of Physics* 12:075020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/12/7/075020>.
- Metzler, Florian, Camden Hunt, Peter L. Hagelstein, and Nicola Galvanetto. 2024. "Known Mechanisms That Increase Nuclear Fusion Rates in the Solid State." *New Journal of Physics* 26:101202. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1367-2630/ad091c>.
- Paetz gen. Schieck, Hans. 2010. "The Status of 'Polarized Fusion'." *European Physical Journal A* 44:321–354. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epja/i2010-10979-6>.
- Pálffy, Adriana, and Sergey V. Popruzhenko. 2020. "Can Extreme Electromagnetic Fields Accelerate the α Decay of Nuclei?" *Physical Review Letters* 124 (21): 212505. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.124.212505>.
- Qi, J.-T., Z.-Y. Zhou, and X. Wang. 2026. "Theory of Laser-Assisted Nuclear Fusion." *Nuclear Science and Techniques* 37:53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41365-025-01826-y>.
- Quaglioni, Sofia, Petr Navrátil, Robert Roth, and Wataru Horiuchi. 2012. "From Nucleons to Nuclei to Fusion Reactions." In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 402:012037. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/402/1/012037>.
- Queisser, Friedemann, and Ralf Schützhold. 2019. "Dynamically Assisted Nuclear Fusion." *Physical Review C* 100 (4): 041601. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.100.041601>.
- Raiola, F., et al. 2006. "Electron Screening: A Review." In *AIP Conference Proceedings*, 831:296–303. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2200959>.
- Röhlsberger, R., K. Schlage, B. Sahoo, S. Couet, and R. Ruffer. 2010. "Collective Lamb Shift in Single-Photon Superradiance." *Science* 328 (5983): 1248–1251. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1187770>.
- Ryndyk, Daniil, Christian Kohlfürst, Friedemann Queisser, and Ralf Schützhold. 2024. "Dynamically Assisted Tunneling in the Floquet Picture." *Physical Review Research* 6 (2): 023056. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.6.023056>.
- Salpeter, Edwin E. 1952. "Nuclear Reactions in the Stars. I. Proton-Proton Chain." *Physical Review* 88 (3): 547–553. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.88.547>.
- Shirokov, A. M., G. Papadimitriou, A. I. Mazur, I. A. Mazur, R. Roth, and J. P. Vary. 2016. "Prediction for a Four-Neutron Resonance." *Physical Review Letters* 117 (18): 182502. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.117.182502>.

- Shoppa, T. D., S. E. Koonin, K. Langanke, and R. Seki. 1993. "One- and Two-Electron Atomic Screening in Fusion Reactions." *Physical Review C* 48 (2): 837–840. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.48.837>.
- Solovyev, A. S., et al. 2024. "Exploring the ${}^2\text{H}(d, p){}^3\text{H}$ and ${}^2\text{H}(d, n){}^3\text{He}$ Fusion Reactions within the Microscopic Multichannel Cluster Approach in Oscillator Representation." *European Physical Journal A* 60:83. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epja/s10050-024-01253-2>.
- Terhune, J. H., and G. C. Baldwin. 1965. "Nuclear Superradiance in Solids." *Physical Review Letters* 14:589–591. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.14.589>.
- Tichai, Alexander, Roman Schutski, Gustavo E. Scuseria, and Thomas Duguet. 2019. "Tensor-Decomposition Techniques for Ab Initio Nuclear Structure Calculations: From Chiral Nuclear Potentials to Ground-State Energies." *Physical Review C* 99 (3): 034320. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.99.034320>.
- Viviani, M., L. Girlanda, A. Kievsky, and L. E. Marcucci. 2023. "Theoretical Study of the $d(d, p){}^3\text{H}$ and $d(d, n){}^3\text{He}$ Processes at Low Energies." *Physical Review Letters* 130 (12): 122501. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.130.122501>.
- Xu, Y., K. Takahashi, S. Goriely, M. Arnould, M. Ohta, and H. Utsunomiya. 2013. "NACRE II: An Update of the NACRE Compilation of Charged-Particle-Induced Thermonuclear Reaction Rates for Nuclei with Mass Number $A < 16$." *Nuclear Physics A* 918:61–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nuclphysa.2013.09.007>.